

Teacher Effectiveness of College teachers with Relation to Self-efficacy and Demographic variables

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Abstract

A teacher plays an important and effective role in education process. An effective teacher influences the entire teaching-learning process directly and indirectly. So, a teacher must be effective for achieving the ultimate aim of education. The teacher effectiveness is likely to be influenced by many factors as school climate, classroom management, student's achievement and others. Self-efficacy is one of the factors which affect teacher effectiveness. Therefore, in the present study researchers examined the relationship between teacher effectiveness and self-efficacy and demographic variables as gender, type of colleges and high qualification of college teachers. 8 colleges were selected randomly which were affiliated to CCS University Meerut, and then 120 teachers were selected through quota sampling. The sample was truly representative for male-female, govt./aided-self-financed and Ph.D-Non Ph.D. Two tools were used for collecting data: 1. Teacher Effectiveness Scale developed by Puri and Gakhar (2005), 2. Teacher's sense of Self-efficacy Scale developed by Moran and Hoy (2001). The result of the study showed that gender, type of colleges and high qualification did not affect to teacher effectiveness and also found the positive correlation between level of self-efficacy and teacher effectiveness.

Keywords: Teacher Effectiveness, Level of Self-efficacy, Demographic Variables, College Teachers.

Introduction

As a seed needs a very good take care of a gardener for growing up as a tree with full of fruits and flowers as like a child needs a teacher for helping and guiding him to grow up as a successful man in his life. When we talk about a teacher many educators define it in his own words. A teacher not only teaches a child but also influenced him from his personality. Well said by Dr. Radhakrishna 'Teacher's place in society is of vital important. He acts as the point of transmission of intellectual tradition and technical skill from generation to generation and helps to keep the lamp of civilization burning.' A teacher never replaced by any machine or any

technology in education because teacher has many qualities, effectiveness and values which helps his students to develop emotionally, socially, economically and also affectively. An effective teacher can achieve the ultimate aim of education as all round development of students' personality. Walls (1999) summarized the most prevalent recommendations from the teaching effectiveness under four heading i.e. the four aces of teaching: outcomes, clarity, engagement and enthusiasm.

These four aces of teaching can make student-learning more effective and longer. More effective teacher provides proper direction and guidance to their students. An effective teacher always focus on their outcomes, clarity of their content, students engagement in teaching-learning process and make their teaching interesting. Well said by someone, if you hate to teach it, your students will hate to learn it. Flander's and Simon (1969) define teaching effectiveness "An area of research concerned teacher, teaching acts and their impact on educational outcomes". Teaching effectiveness is a combination of cognitive-non-cognitive, academic-non-academic, formal-informal qualities as like attitude, aptitude, thought process, communication skill, methods of teaching, expression, experiences, social-personal interaction etc. Some studies showed the positive relationship between teaching effectiveness and independent variables like job satisfaction, achievement of students, organizational climate, administrative behavior, teacher efficacy and others. There are many more factors which have definite impact on teacher effectiveness; self-efficacy is one of those factors. Bandura (1977) noted that self-efficacy belief have a great impact on peoples 'cognitive, motivation, affective and selection process. According to him "People beliefs in their efficacy affect almost everything they do: how they think, motivate themselves and behave". Teachers' self-efficacy belief is that teachers' belief in his own abilities, his potential to do things effectively and skillfully to attain educational goals.

The teacher' self-efficacy plays an important role for a teacher and their teaching effectiveness in term of knowledge, classroom management skill, their personality etc. so this study will explore the relationship between teacher effectiveness and self-efficacy of college teachers.

Review of Related Literature

The reviews of related literature promote a comprehensive view and better understanding of the problem. It also helps to analysis and synthesis the current situation in which a problem does exist. A researcher should develop great understanding regarding problem before start his investigation. Keeping in the mind the importance of reviewing the literature, some studies are presented here to understand this study as follow:

Singh (1993) examined the relation of teacher effectiveness with their gender, area of teaching and adjustment on 330 higher secondary schools teachers. The results revealed that urban teachers have more adjustment ability rather than rural teachers. **Gupta (1995)** found the relationship between job satisfaction and teacher effectiveness in his study which was conducted on secondary school teachers of Ghaziabad (U.P.). He found significant co-relation between

overall dimensions of job satisfaction of teacher (salary benefits, family life etc.) with teacher effectiveness. **Sikora (1997)** also examined the relationship between personality types and teacher effectiveness of FCS (Family and Consumer Science) teachers from three school districts in Eastern Tennessee. He found in his research that teacher's personality may play a significant but a limited role in teacher effectiveness.

Pandey and Maikhuri (1999) conducted their study on the attitude of effective and ineffective teachers towards their profession. They found major findings regarding experience, age and attitude towards teaching as no significant difference between effective teachers having high and low experience, high experienced teacher's attitude was positive towards teaching than low experience ineffective teachers.

Vijaylakshmi (2002) studied the importance of sex, marital status, educational qualification, experiences, subject of teaching, age, designation, types of colleges and management on teacher effectiveness. They found only teachers, those having their age up to 35 years have significant difference and other did not have any significant influence on the teacher effectiveness. **Amandeep and Gurpreet (2005)** interpreted the significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and teaching competency. The result of the study showed that female teachers are more effective in their teaching and has not significant difference as far as their competency. **Roul (2007)** found in his study that the teachers of autonomous colleges were more effective than the teachers of non-autonomous colleges. He also found the non-autonomous colleges teachers has burdened of more work and has not more freedom to do their work.

Objectives of the study

Following are the objectives of the study:

1. To explore the present status of teacher effectiveness of college teachers.
2. To find out the impact of gender on teacher effectiveness of college teachers.
3. To find out the impact of type of colleges on teacher effectiveness of college teachers.
4. To find out the impact of higher qualification on teacher effectiveness of college teacher
5. To find out the relation between teacher effectiveness and teachers' self-efficacy of college teachers
6. To find out the impact of self-efficacy on teacher effectiveness of college teachers.

Hypotheses of the study

Keeping objectives of the study in mind following hypotheses are framed:

1. There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of male college teachers and female college teachers.
2. There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of Govt./Aided college teachers and Self-financed college teachers.
3. There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of Ph.D college teachers and non Ph.D college teachers.

4. There is no significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and self-efficacy of college teachers.
5. There is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of college teachers having high self-efficacy and low self-efficacy.

Methodology of the study

The present study explores the teacher effectiveness of college teachers with the relation to self efficacy and demographic variables as gender, type of colleges and higher qualification of college teachers. The researcher adopted descriptive method of research for this purpose.

The target population of the present study is comprised all the college teachers working under Govt./Aided and Self-financed colleges affiliated to CCS University Meerut. First randomization was done to select Govt./Aided colleges and Self-financed colleges. Total 8 colleges were selected then 120 teachers were taken in the sample through quota sampling in such a way that both male and female and Ph.D and non Ph.D will truly represent the sample.

In the present study teacher effectiveness of college teachers was treated as dependent variable and self-efficacy of teachers, gender, types of colleges and higher qualification of teachers were considered as independent variables.

For collecting the data related to teacher effectiveness of college teachers the researchers used The Teacher Effectiveness Scale which was developed by Puri and Gakhar(2005). This test has been developed in Indian conditions. There are 68 statements which belonged to the 6 teacher behavior categories and the reliability of the test is 0.76 with good content validity. The scoring of the data is on 5 point scale.

Teacher's sense of Self-efficacy Scale was used for collecting the data that was originally developed by Moran and Hoy (2001). It has adopted in Indian conditions and the final draft of the tool has 30 items which measured teachers' sense of efficacy in the areas of instructional strategies (10 items), classroom management (10 items) and students engagement (10 items) respectively. Teachers rated their responses on a 5-point Likert scale from 'Nothing' (1) to 'A great deal' (5). Originally this tool was developed in USA thus its reliability and validity were re-established. A group of teachers (N=30) was selected for pilot study. The reliability of adapted tool was .894, which indicates the good internal consistency of tool.

Analysis and Interpretation of study

In the present study the researchers used and explained the data from the sample to explore the teacher effectiveness of the college teachers with relation to self-efficacy and demographic variables.

1. *Status of Teacher Effectiveness:* Before analyzing the data of teacher effectiveness the researcher showed the status of teacher effectiveness of college teachers in the following table 1:

Table 1: Status of Teacher Effectiveness of College Teachers

Mean	SD	QD	Sk	Ku	Min.Score	Max.Score
298.98	24.3	340	-0.49	0.232	212	338

Table 1 showed the status of teacher effectiveness of college teachers as the average of scores is 298.98. The range of scores is 126. There is negative skewness value of data which shows the data is left side longer, means the scores of teacher effectiveness lies more in negative side on NPC.

Researchers showed the demographic characteristics of college teachers in the following table 2:

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of College Teachers (N=120)

S.N.	VARIABLES	FREQUENCES	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	GENDER		
	Male	51	42.5
	Female	69	57.5
2..	TYPE OF COLLEGES		
	Govt./Aided	60	50
	Self-financed	60	50
3.	HIGHER(Academic) QUALIFICATION		
	Ph.D	73	60.8
	Non-Ph.D	47	39.2

Table 2 shows demographic characteristics of college teachers. It shows that 57.5% of sample is female college teachers and Ph.D holders are 60.8%, which indicates good level of educational qualification.

2. Impact of demographic characteristics on teacher effectiveness

Here the result presented under table 3, 4 and 5. The tables are as follow:

Table 3: Gender wise difference in Teacher Effectiveness of College Teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
Male	51	295.84	21.54	118	0.226	Not Significant
Female	69	301.29	26.06			

This table shows that there is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of college teachers with respect to gender is retained. It means male and female both did not have any influence on teacher effectiveness.

Table 4: Type of College wise difference in Teacher Effectiveness of College Teachers

Type of Colleges	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
Govt./Aided	60	299.62	23.46	118	0.773	Not Significant
Self-Financed	60	298.33	25.28			

This table concluded that the type of colleges (govt./aided) did not have any impact on teacher effectiveness of teachers. The mean scores of college teacher also have approx. same value.

Table 5: Qualification wise difference in Teacher Effectiveness of College Teachers

Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
Ph.D	73	302.79	25.097	118	0.0312	Not Significant
Non-Ph.D	47	293.04	21.963			

This table interpreted that qualification wise there is no significant difference in teacher effectiveness of teachers at 0.05 levels. The mean score of Ph.D holders have higher mean value rather than to Non-Ph.D holder teachers.

The researchers also showed the mean scores of demographic variables wise of college teachers as a graph:

Graph1: Mean Scores of level of self-efficacy and demographic variables wise College Teachers

Table 6: Difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Teachers having high and low Self-efficacy

Level of Self-efficacy	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
High	40	313.92	23.37	78	5.68	Significant
Low	40	284.22	20.78			

Table 6 unveil that the teachers having high self-efficacy and low self efficacy are significantly different on teacher effectiveness. It can be said that the teachers having high self efficacy are higher in teacher effectiveness.

To seek the relation between teacher effectiveness and self-efficacy of college teachers, correlation coefficient through product moment method was calculated. It was 0.428 which was positive and moderate in nature. Table 7 showed the coefficient of Co-relation as:

Table 7: Relation between Teacher Effectiveness and Self-efficacy of College Teachers

Variable 1	Variable 2	Coefficient of Co-relation
Teacher effectiveness 199.48	Self-efficacy 299.08	0.428

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Thus, it is clear that teacher effectiveness and self efficacy are related i.e., when self efficacy of teacher will increase teacher effectiveness will also increase.

Conclusion

An effective teacher have many qualities with mastery of his subject as like classroom management, leadership qualities, positive attitude, social interpersonal relations, cooperative behavior etc. In this study, it was found that Gender, Type of Colleges and Academic Qualification did not affect teacher effectiveness. It was also found that high and low level of Self-efficacy affects College teacher effectiveness. Teachers who have high self-efficacy, its effectiveness also will be high and reversely have low self-efficacy, its effectiveness also will be low. It was found the positive Correlation in self efficacy and teacher effectiveness. So teacher should be more effective, motivational, innovative and have high self- efficacy belief. Hence the policy makers, administrator, college management and other authority should more conscious about the effectiveness of college teachers.

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